

****Request for Legal Counsel - AI Safety Whistleblower, Good-Faith Disclosure Dismissed, Federal Non-Response**

From: [REDACTED]

To: clinic@cyber.harvard.edu [REDACTED]

Date: 4/8/26 1:05 PM

Dear Harvard law Cyber Clinic,

I'm reaching out again as I have not received a response regarding my prior email. In the time since my last email my research corpus on zenodo has grown to 28 records with over 4k cumulative views and an 82% download rate which in the niche ai alignment and safety field is "viral". I have also uploaded the letters sent to relevant congressional committees along with approximately 10gb of Proof of Concept videos with delivery receipts. I will be posting this email as well to support transparency and my efforts at full disclosure

If you have no interest in this or do not find my situation as meeting your mission statement I respectfully request that you please inform me as I have spent over 6 months trying to report these grave vulnerabilities with no substantive contact and their continued exploitability in critical infrastructure, defense and healthcare industries.

The disclosure record is here:

<https://zenodo.org/records/19444222>

Sent from [Proton Mail](#) for Android.